

PAVING THE WAY FOR A NEXT GENERATION BIOBUTANOL (BUTANEXT)

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ABSTRACT: Biofuels are considered to be the most promising substitutes for the decarbonisation of the transport sector, especially heavy road and air transport. For this reason new and more sustainable drop-in biofuel alternatives are being pursued with the aim of overcoming the current challenges and limitations exhibited by 1st generation biofuels through R&D projects such as Next Generation Butanol (ButaNexT). The ButaNexT project aims to develop a highly efficient production process for the conversion of sustainable lignocellulosic feedstocks into bio-butanol through the integration of different technology developments. Begun in 2015, the project aims to develop, optimise and integrate several novel and advanced technologies for the production of sustainable, more efficient and versatile biobutanol from lignocellulosic feedstocks and wastes. The following article shows the main achievements to date of the ButaNexT project towards developing next generation biobutanol.

Keywords: liquid biofuel, fermentation, miscanthus, wheat straw, pilot plant, sustainability

1 INTRODUCTION

The transport sector is still highly dependent on fossil energy carriers and is responsible for a quarter of EU greenhouse gas emissions. Across all transport modes, the major energy consumer is road transport which represents 81.7%, followed by air (13.9%), rail (2%) and water (1.6%) [1]. Biofuels are considered to be the most promising substitutes for the decarbonisation of the transport sector, especially heavy road and air transport, despite a recent dip in biofuel consumption due to lower oil price and concerns around sustainability of first generation biofuels (i.e. iLUC (1)). In fact, biofuel consumption in 2015 accounted for 14 Mtoe (19% bioethanol and 81% biodiesel) of which 91% was certified as sustainable [2]. For this reason new and more sustainable drop-in biofuel alternatives are being pursued with the aim of overcoming the current challenges and limitations exhibited by bioethanol and biodiesel through R&D projects as Next Generation Butanol (ButaNexT).

The ButaNexT project aims to develop a highly efficient production process for the conversion of sustainable lignocellulosic feedstocks into biobutanol through the integration of different technology developments.

Butanol is a four carbon alcohol that can be used as a transport fuel. It has traditionally been produced by ABE (2) fermentation (the anaerobic conversion of carbohydrates by strains of *Clostridium* into acetone, butanol and ethanol). However, there are some important techno-economic issues with ABE fermentation: costs, the relatively low-yield and sluggish fermentations, and some problems caused by end product inhibition and phage infections, made ABE butanol uncompetitive on a commercial scale with butanol produced synthetically from oil and almost all ABE production ceased as the petrochemical industry evolved.

Nevertheless, there is now increasing interest in use

of biobutanol as a transport fuel. In fact, 85% Butanol/gasoline blends can be used in unmodified petrol engines. It can be transported in existing gasoline pipelines and produces more power per litre than ethanol. [3].

Existing biobutanol production is largely from sugars, whereas this project targets lignocellulosic feedstocks including cereal straw and energy crops.

The following article describes the main key achievements of the ButaNexT project to date.

2 OVERVIEW

The ButaNexT project started in May 2015 with the aim to develop, optimise and integrate several novel and advanced technologies for the production of sustainable, more efficient and versatile biobutanol from lignocellulosic feedstocks and wastes. This is expected to be achieved by addressing the following technical, economic and environmental challenges:

- Efficient Conversion of Lignocellulosic Feedstocks into Fermentable Sugars through physical and thermochemical pretreatment and enzymatic hydrolysis.
- High Productivity Fermentation for Biobutanol with “in-situ” product recovery.
- Process Integration and Scale-up.
- Techno/Economic Feasibility of Advanced Biofuels Production.
- Blending and Performance.
- Environmental and Social Benefits Assessment of Advanced Biofuels Production.

The ButaNexT project is currently in its third year, and very significant results have been achieved so far, for example the design and construction of a prototype for physical pretreatment of biomass.

As described in a former proceeding from the 24EUBCE [4], the project is structured in seven workpackages as shown in the following figure:

Figure 1: ButaNexT WP Scheme

At this moment Work Package (WP) 2 and 3 have almost finished their activities and most of the effort is concentrated in the start of the pilot plant activities comprised in WP4. Additionally, WP5 and WP6 continue with the projected tasks.

The main feedstocks used for the development of the process have been miscanthus and wheat straw. The organic fraction of municipal solid waste was also considered in principle but was finally rejected due to its low sugar content that cannot make the conversion process economically viable at this stage in its development.

3 MAIN KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

The following section describes the main achievements of the ButaNexT project up to its second year of life.

3.1 Design and construction of a prototype for physical pre-treatment of biomass.

The objective of the physical pre-treatment stage was the development of an efficient micronizing unit able to precisely control particle size output in the range 150-450 μm , which is required to increase the accessible surface area, thus, improving the hydrolysis yield during thermochemical pre-treatment stage. The design and construction was divided in two main stages, the first one was the design and the prototype construction (which was reported in Del Campo et al [4]), and the second stage has been the particle size optimization study, including energy and costs evaluation.

During the design stage the selection of each of the prototype elements, namely, mill, sieves, mass transport system, was carried out based on performance, energy consumption and safety. The resulting pre-treatment micronizing prototype (figure 2) has two main characteristics:

- Precise particle size control obtained with a combination of a cutting mill and in line continuous sieve that recirculate the feedstock to ensure the correct final particle size.
- A transport system based on a three air cyclones interconnected and assisted by an automatic control unit that ensures mass transport with minimal emission of particulates.

Figure 2: Pre-treatment micronizing unit

In parallel with the design stage particle size optimisation studies have been carried out with the selected equipment aiming to maximise process yield. The final optimized output obtained for both feedstocks has been 7 kg/h, an increase of 28.6 % compared to the output initially targeted in the ButaNexT project of 0.5-5 kg/h. Furthermore, the particle size studies showed that the optimum particle size is 410 μm for miscanthus and 490 μm for wheat straw.

3.2 Development of a thermochemical pretreatment for low and high temperature operation.

There are three main goals in this task in order to make the cellulose polymers accessible for further conversion. First, is necessary to achieve a liquid fraction rich in xylose (Xyl) content; second, to identify and reduce the content of inhibitors in the liquid fraction, and third, to avoid the degradation of the cellulose fraction into C6 sugars (Glucose (GI) hydrolyzed or lost). Two different thermochemical pretreatment technologies (low solids batch and high solid continuous) are being used by TR and CENER respectively, for the purposes above mentioned.

Since the chemical pre-treatment stage is aimed at producing the precursor for a specific task in the biobutanol production process, the identification of inhibitors was heavily based on the requirements of the project. The inhibitors selected as potential objectives the following ones: 5- Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), Furfural (FF), Acetic acid (AA), Levulinic acid (LA), Formic acid (FA). While all inhibitors play a role of degrading performance yield, special emphasis was put on AA and FF due to its high concentration and their effect on the following process stages.

A thermochemical pre-treatment study was carried out for wheat straw and miscanthus. The main outcomes are:

- There is a clear indication that the sulphuric acid concentration plays a key role in the production of inhibitors. Also, while temperature and time did not affect much in inhibitors production, they play an important role in sugar production
- Based on the results from the statistical analysis the optimal operation conditions have been chosen to be the lowest liquid/solid ratio, lowest sulphuric acid content and lowest time, combined with the highest operation temperature.
- The results of the reproducibility study confirmed the model estimations. In the case of miscanthus, the

study returned higher values than expected for almost all the targeted elements. This is a positive outcome since values for glucose and inhibitors were kept within the acceptable range while xylose concentration increased by 9%.

- Studies demonstrated that the sieving stage can be removed with minor impact on performance and up to 88% and 89.5% reduction (for wheat straw and miscanthus, respectively) in energy consumption and processing time in the micronizing stage.
- The slurry obtained after the optimal thermochemical pre-treatment, was divided in two main flows (solid and liquid fraction) by filtration. Finally the glucans content of solid fraction (76%w/w moisture) was 60.3 and 56 % w/w for miscanthus and wheat straw respectively, although the objective of xylose content of the liquid fraction (20-25g/l) was achieved for miscanthus and wheat straw. This was slightly lower than the targeted glucans content of 65%-70%. The xylose released were 24 g/l and 25.5 g/l for miscanthus and wheat straw respectively.

TR has also carried out a study for the concentration and detoxification of the xylose fraction obtained after the pretreatment by filtration. In this study, the liquid fraction (≈ 20 g sugar/l) was filtered using a nanofiltration unit (GEOSMONICS SEPA CF2 figure 3). Initially 6 membranes were tested but 3 were selected as the most efficient ones (KOCH MPF-34, OSMONICS DL and OSMONICS DS). The selected membranes are not permeable to the sugars, however are permeable to the inhibitors, based in this capacity, during the filtration process the sugar content is increased in the retentate (concentrate) by means of volume reduction, whereas the inhibitors are transferred to the permeate.

Figure 3: Nanofiltration unit.

The results obtained showed:

- The sugar recovery was close to 99 % for the three types of membranes.
- The highest sugar content achieved after concentration stage was 70.5 g sugar/l (KOCH MPF-34).
- The lowest inhibitors contents were achieved using OSMONICS DL membrane, where 77.5% and 96.3 % of the FF and AA were removed. These final concentrations were below the set thresholds.
- Although the sugar content obtained using the OSMONICS DL membrane was slightly lower (69.8g sugar/L), the higher removal of inhibitors and the large reduction in operation time, 8 hours instead 30 hours indicates that the OSMONICS DL membrane was the most

suitable membrane to concentrate the sugars and remove the inhibitors of the liquid fraction obtained after thermochemical pretreatment.

The thermochemical pre-treatment study at high solids and temperature was carried out by CENER for wheat straw and miscanthus. For optimization, 3 acid – catalyst concentrations (1-2-2.5%) and temperatures (160-175-190°C) were considered for a residence time of 5 min. The slurry samples were subjected to a saccharification step in order to quantify the suitability/adaptability of each thermochemical pretreatment condition by means of final sugar solubilization (glucose, xylose and arabinose). Best pretreatment conditions were selected based on: higher total soluble sugars hydrolyzed after saccharification, low inhibitors concentration (basically furfurals and acetic acid) while keeping thermochemical pretreatment variables (temperature and catalyst concentration) as mild as possible. In the following figures are depicted the regression curves of total soluble sugars against acid (%w/w) and temperature (°C) (after 72 hours of saccharification) for miscanthus and wheat straw (Fig. 4 A &B).

Figure 4: Regression curve of Total soluble sugars against acid (%w/w) and temperature (°C) at 72 hours of saccharification of miscanthus (A) and wheat straw (B).

Considering the above mentioned premises, best thermochemical pretreatment conditions for each feedstock coincided in subjecting both feedstocks to an acid concentration of 2% and the temperature of 175°C for 5 min. Under these conditions xylose concentration after thermochemical pretreatment reaches approximately 61g/L and 57 g/L for miscanthus and wheat straw respectively; furfurals (5Hydroxymethylfurfural and

furfural) and acetic acid concentration reach up to 2.6 and 9.5 g/L respectively for miscanthus and 1.5g/L and 4.4 g/L respectively for wheat straw. Finally, total soluble sugars obtained after saccharification (at 10% by weight of total solids) were around 55 g/L and 64 g/L for miscanthus and wheat straw respectively.

3.3 Development of tailored enzyme cocktails for improved hydrolysis of pretreated lignocellulosic biomass

MetGen's activities towards the development and optimization of tailored MetZyme® SUNO™ drop-in enzymatic solutions for the efficient saccharification of selected pretreated feedstocks - wheat straw and miscanthus – have resulted in clear improvements compared to the initial offering (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Illustration of progressive improvements in total sugar yields for pretreated wheat straw (upper) and miscanthus (lower) achieved with different enzyme cocktail formulations (BC0: initial offering) during the optimization work conducted by MetGen in ButaNext. Results refer to sugar yields after 72 h hydrolysis.

The subsequent optimization rounds have led to almost 90% improvement in total sugar yield compared to the initial offering in the case of pretreated wheat straw, whereas for pretreated miscanthus, the increase was almost 70%. In addition, in most cases 80-90% of recoverable sugars were released already after 24h of hydrolysis, indicating a clear improvement in hydrolysis rate. The high efficiency of the improved enzyme formulations towards the conversion of glucan to glucose was further confirmed by a pilot assay conducted in CENER facilities. In the case of wheat straw, glucan **saccharification yield** has improved from 67-70.5% up to **100%** when using the improved enzyme formulation for 144h; while for Miscanthus the glucan **saccharification yield** has been increased from 63% up to **82.4%**, maximum achieved when employing the improved formulation for 88 h. As a result, for wheat straw, total soluble sugars concentration at the end of saccharification (at 20% by weight of total solids) exceed 120g/L.

On top of the technical performance, other aspects were also considered during the development work, including upscalability (i.e. complexity of the formulations, whether components are powder or solutions), production cost (i.e. cost of components, complexity of formulation). These considerations enabled finding of more economical feasible alternatives with

similar technical performance. In addition, a round of Clostridium fermentation bottle-scale experiments for solvent production was also conducted by Green Biologics (GBL) using hydrolysates produced with the most promising candidates. These tests indicated that all hydrolysates produced by the most promising enzyme cocktails were fermentable.

Already during the development and optimization phase, MetGen has been able to supply 27 kg of its initial offering and 35 L of improved enzymatic solution to ButaNext consortium. This further confirms MetGen's capability to produce and supply these enzyme solutions in required quantities and in a timely manner for subsequent larger scale assays in ButaNext for biobutanol production. This is possible due to utilization of MetGen's technology platform ENZINE® which allows fast, flexible and adaptable development of tailor-made enzyme solutions from lab-scale to industrial scale for biorefinery applications.

3.4 Development of a Clostridial strain able to ferment cellulosic sugar effectively

GBL developed butanol tolerant strains using adaptive laboratory evolution. The resulting mutants produced over 20 % higher maximum butanol titres than the control strains and showed significant increases in sugar uptake rate at these higher butanol concentrations (Fig 6). Butanol yields in this system could not be quantified due to the method of solvent removal, however when tested in GBL's Advanced Fermentation Process™ (AFP), the strain achieved 76 % of the target yield based on carbon used. It is expected that the yield target can be obtained at pilot scale due to improved solvent capture capability.

Figure 6: Normalised sugar uptake rate and maximum butanol titre of GBL developed strains

Mutant strain 1 was taken forward for further testing in VITO's process intensification activities.

Strains were also developed with improved tolerance to inhibitors present in a representative cellulosic feedstock. These strains exceeded the target for solvent productivity by 75% and 21% respectively when tested on miscanthus and wheat straw hydrolysates in GBL's AFP™ system and are also under assessment in this project.

3.5 Development of a patent-pending "In situ product recovery process"

In conventional ABE fermentation, the acetone, butanol and ethanol titers remain rather low (~2% solvents) due to severe product inhibition, which leads to high steam consumption and high waste water volumes

per kilogram solvent. *In situ* recovery of the solvents can alleviate product inhibition effects and can be achieved through the integration of organophilic pervaporation in the fermentation process.

VITO thoroughly evaluated the difference in performance between fed-batch and continuous fermentations coupled to several organophilic pervaporation membranes. The bacterial cells were always freely suspended and the in-house designed and constructed organophilic pervaporation units were directly coupled to the fermentors, without intermediate cell retention step.

It was found that while both fed-batch and continuous conditions were compatible with organophilic pervaporation operations, continuous conditions have the edge over (fed-)batch conditions in terms of labour intensity, water consumption, solvent concentration in the permeate, volumetric productivity and base consumption.

Of the tested pervaporation membranes, one was identified with optimal total fluxes of $0.9 - 1.39 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and solvent concentrations of $123 - 247 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ in the condensate. Both fluxes and solvent concentrations in the condensate depended on the residual solvent concentrations in the fermentor. No flux decline, i.e. no membrane fouling, was observed over several weeks of operation.

Solvent (acetone-butanol-ethanol) productivities up to $0.97 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ were obtained in continuous conditions. While glucose was completely consumed, a trade-off between xylose utilization and productivity was shown: the higher the productivity, the lower the xylose utilization. Therefore, an economic optimum has to be established between fermentor size (with an impact on capital costs) and substrate costs (as defined by carbohydrate utilization).

The integrated concept with pervaporation leads to significant reductions in steam consumption and waste water production per kilogram solvent [5]. The energy consumption can even be further reduced through a patent pending improvement.

3.6 Validation of the integrated process at a pilot plant

One of the specific objectives of the project is the validation of the technical performance of the whole ButaNexT process (from feedstock handling to product separation) in a centralised pilot facility. This facility is located at CENER's Second Generation Biofuels Centre (CB2G) in Aoiz (Spain) and is composed of the following units:

- Mechanical pretreatment prototype developed for the project by Técnicas Reunidas and temporarily transferred to CENER's premises.
- Thermochemical pretreatment reactor
- Enzymatic hydrolysis reactor
- Filtration unit
- Seed propagation equipment and fermentor
- Pervaporation unit prototype developed for the project by VITO and temporarily transferred to CENER's premises.

The following figure shows the integrated flowchart of the process.

Figure 7: Integrated flowchart of ButaNexT process

The pilot plant runs will be carried out by CENER using wheat straw and miscanthus as feedstocks. Before starting operation training activities have been carried out with the support of some of the partners (TR, GBL and VITO).

The main outcome of this task will be a technical report on the validation of performance data at pilot scale using wheat straw and miscanthus to produce butanol.

3.7 Evaluation of butanol as a blend component with fossil fuels

After the work done around fuel and blend properties, the most promising blends were tested in a Euro 6 engine on an engine test bench under ambient temperature to assess the performance and gaseous and particle emissions of butanol blends under NEDC (New European Driving Cycle), which was simulated with a Road Load Simulation (RLS) system. The studied blends are the following (all in volume basis):

- Binary blends: Bu10D (10% butanol-90% diesel), Bu20D (20% butanol-80% diesel)
- Ternary blend (10% butanol, 10% biodiesel and 80% diesel).

The engine tested is a Nissan K9K engine, typically equipped in European medium-size (Figure 8)

Figure 8: Nissan K9K engine

During urban subcycles, NOx instantaneous emissions (Figure 9) decrease as the engine gets hotter.

They become much more intense from the start of the extra-urban cycle for all fuels, as a consequence of the sudden increase of load. More than 60% of the total NO_x emissions occurred in the extra-urban subcycle, in all cases. NO_x emissions at the end of the cycle were lowest for Diesel and Bu20D fuels and slightly higher for Bu10D and Bu10B10D fuels. Such slight emissions increases were mainly based on higher instantaneous emissions during extra-urban accelerations.

Figure 9: NO_x instantaneous emissions during NEDC cycle

Particle mass emissions were measured upstream of the particulate filter. The highest rate of particle formation and emissions were observed in the extra-urban accelerations, mainly due to higher equivalence ratios. Also significant emission rates are observed in the urban accelerations when the engine is still cold. As it gets hotter, the emission rates decrease substantially. Regarding the effect of the fuel used, when the engine gets hot enough, the rate of emissions becomes substantially lower for butanol blends, and especially for the ternary blend. The main benefit of oxygenated fuels with respect to diesel fuel occurs during the extra-urban subcycle.

Figure 10: Particle mass instantaneous emissions during NEDC cycle

3.8 Calculation of GHG emissions of biobutanol in different scenarios

An initial mass and energy balance of the ButaNexT biobutanol production process at commercial scale has been developed, in order to assess the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with the fuel. The methodology laid out in the EU Renewable Energy Directive [6] was used to assess the GHG emissions of biobutanol produced from both Miscanthus and wheat straw. Several scenarios for the provision of heat, electricity and waste water treatment at the plant were considered. Emissions savings compared to the fossil fuel comparator ranged from 49% to 87% depending on

feedstock and process conditions, showing that biobutanol produced using the ButaNexT process would have significant GHG reductions compared to fossil fuels, and could be competitive on a GHG basis with 1st generation biofuels.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The development of a sustainable process to produce butanol from lignocellulosic residues is becoming a reality thanks to the achievements of the ButaNexT project. Although there is still one year until the end of the project, some interesting lessons learnt can be reported:

- The final optimised milled feedstock output obtained for both biomass types (wheat straw and miscanthus) has been improved to 7 kg/h, an improvement of 28.6 % compared to the output initially targeted in the ButaNexT project of 0.5-5 kg/h. Furthermore, the particle size studies showed that the optimum particle size is 410 μ m for miscanthus and 490 μ m for wheat straw.
- The best (low-solids and temperature) thermochemical pre-treatment conditions for both feedstock are the lowest liquid/solid ratio, lowest sulphuric acid content and lowest time, combined with the highest operation temperature. Using these conditions, the glucans content of solid fraction (76%w/w moisture) was 60.3 and 56 % w/w for miscanthus and wheat straw respectively, and the xylose content of the liquid fraction was 24 g/L for miscanthus and 25.5 g/L for wheat straw respectively.
- Nanofiltration using membrane OSMONICS DL has proven to be an effective technique for sugar concentration after pre-treatment, achieving a sugar concentration of 69.8g/L, furthermore the inhibitors removed using this membrane were 77.5% and 96.3 % of the FF and AA respectively
- The best (high-solids) thermochemical pretreatment conditions for both feedstocks are the same ones (acid concentration of 2% ; 175°C for 5 min). Under these conditions xylose concentration reaches approximately 61 g/L and 57 g/L for miscanthus and wheat straw respectively; furfurals (5Hydroxymethylfurfural and furfural) and acetic acid concentration reach up to 2.6 and 9.5 g/L respectively for miscanthus and 1.5g/L and 4.4 g/L respectively for wheat straw. Furthermore, total soluble sugars obtained after saccharification (at 10% by weight of total solids) were around 55 g/L and 64 g/L for miscanthus and wheat straw respectively
- After a series of optimisation rounds almost a 90% improvement in total sugar yield during enzymatic hydrolysis process at lab scale has been achieved compared to the initial offering in the case of pretreated wheat straw, whereas for pretreated miscanthus, the increase was almost 70%. In addition, in most cases 80-90% of recoverable sugars were released already after 24h of hydrolysis, which indicates a clear improvement of the hydrolysis rate. Furthermore pilot plant assays with enzyme cocktail yielded 100% glucan to glucose conversion and 82% for wheat straw and

miscanthus.

- Mutant strains with improved tolerance to inhibitors present in the cellulosic media have been developed. These strains exceeded the target for solvent productivity by 75% and 21% respectively when tested on miscanthus and wheat straw hydrolysates in GBL's AFP™ system and are also under assessment in this project.
- The integrated concept of fermentation coupled with pervaporation leads to significant environmental improvements in terms of steam and energy consumption and waste water production. However, a trade-off between xylose utilization and productivity was shown. Hence, an economic optimum has to be established between capital costs (fermentor size) and substrate costs (as defined by carbohydrate utilization).
- Three butanol blends with fossil fuels have been tested in a Euro 6 engine on an engine test bench under ambient temperature to assess the performance and gaseous and particle emissions of butanol blends under NEDC, with promising reductions in particle emissions upstream of the diesel particulate filter.
- Preliminary GHG emissions savings compared to the fossil fuel comparator ranged from 49% to 87% depending on feedstock and process conditions, showing that biobutanol produced using the ButaNexT process would have significant GHG reductions compared to fossil fuels, and could be competitive on a GHG basis with 1st generation biofuels.

5 NOTES

- (1) iLUC: indirect land use change
- (2) ABE: fermentation process named after the three products; acetone, butanol and ethanol.

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8 LOGO SPACE

BUTANEXT
Next Generation Biobutanol

More information about ButaNexT:

<http://www.butanext.eu>